

REINFORCEMENT MECHANISMS OF LONG FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES: THE ROLE OF THE CARBON INTERPHASE

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ABSTRACT

The microstructural characteristics of the interphases is studied in Nicalon/glass or glass ceramic composites by TEM, HRTEM, SIMS, EDX and EELS. The strength of the composites and of the fibres in the composites is studied by flexural and traction tests respectively. The role of the carbon interphase derived from this study is compared to previous results obtained in Nicalon/SiC and SCS6/TA6V composites. They show that a carbon interphase does not always promote toughness. In the studied composites, the toughness depends on the adhesion of the carbon interphase on the surrounding phases and not on its supposed layered structure.

Keywords: Interface, carbon interphase, composite, fibre, microstructure, toughness, strength.

INTRODUCTION

The aim of the tailoring of the interface is to control the fiber strength and the resistance to debonding and/or to sliding at the interfaces while introducing an appropriate interphase between the fibre and the matrix. Such a tailoring is still empiric and the prediction of its efficiency uncertain. Such is the case of the carbon interphase which has the reputation to promote the composite toughness. The exact role of this carbon interphase was studied in Nicalon/glass or glass-ceramic composites. In such composites, the toughness or the brittleness was related to the presence or the absence of a carbon interphase [1]. To discuss the role of the carbon interphase, the microstructural characteristics of the interphases formed by fibre-matrix reaction in nicalon/glass or glass-ceramic composites were thus correlated to the strength of the composites and of the fibers in the composites.

MATERIALS

1D composites, fabricated with 202 Nicalon fibres (40 vol%) were hot pressed at 1300°C during different times resulting in ten materials (table1). The composition of the fibres used derived from SIMS analysis are in good agreement with previous SIMS analyses performed by the author [2] and XPS analysis realized by Porte and Sartre [3]: Si/C = 0.77 ± 0.7 and O/C = 0.34 ± 0.15 .

TECHNIQUES

The microstructure and composition were investigated by TEM, HTREM, EDX and EELS using a Jeol 2000FX equipped with a Link Si-Li UTW detector and a Gatan PEELS spectrometer. Cross-sections were cut from the different composites perpendicularly to the fibre axis. The variation of composition at the periphery of fibres extracted from every composite by HF etch was investigated by SIMS using a Cameca IMS4F spectrometre with the experimental conditions selected to analyse

the fibre near surface. These analysis were complemented by AES and XPS in the A10 and B10 composites [4]. The strength of the composites were measured during 3 points flexural tests and the strength of the extracted fibres during traction tests.

Table 1: Composites references, fibre and matrix composition, hot pressing time , thermal expansion coefficients

Material	Major components	Minor components	structure	hot pressing time (mn)	α_m ((10 ⁻⁶ K ⁻¹))
fibre	SiC, SiO _x Cy, C	SiO ₂ [3]			3,5
A2	LAS	+ ε MgO	glass	2	3,5
A10	"		"	10	"
A 60	"		"	60	"
B2	LAS+	ε MgO + Nb ₂ O ₅	glass	2	"
B10	"		"	10	"
B60	"		"	60	"
B120	"		"	120	"
D	LAS +	MAS +ZrO ₂ + Nb ₂ O ₅	glass-ceramic	10	1
C	x LAS + y MAS	Nb ₂ O ₅	"	10	0,45
E	x'LAS + y' MAS	Nb ₂ O ₅	"	10	3

MICROSTRUCTURE AND COMPOSITION OF THE INTERPHASES

The study of the microstructure and the composition of the interfaces reveals features which are either characteristic of all the composites or typical of a given composite.

Whatever the elaboration time and matrix composition, the microstructure of the fibre core is not changed by the composite fabrication (fig.1a) whereas the periphery of the fibre is modified. In every composites, the fibre-matrix reaction results in two continuous interphases: a carbon layer (CL) next to the matrix and a transition region (TR) between the CL and the unmodified fibre core (fig. 1b, 2 and 3). Exept in composites A, the CL is edged by a third interphase composed of NbC grains. The common and distinct features of the interphases in the different composites are summarized in table 2 and described in the following.

- NbC layer in B, C, D and E composites:

A discontinuous string of NbC grains, 10 to 50 nm in diametre, edges the CL. The grains are included into the matrix (ex. fig. 3c). In the B composites, the string width ranges from 20 to 100 nm and is only slightly increased by the hot pressing time. Notice also that the width in the E composite varies a lot (80 nm to 1.4 μm) but is much larger than in the B, C and D composites.

- the carbon layer (CL):

The CL thickness strongly depends on the matrix composition (table 2). It is much larger when the matrix contains Nb₂O₅ as demonstrated by the results obtained in composites A and B whose matrices only differs by the addition of Nb₂O₅. This result confirms previous Brennan works [1]. On the contrary, the CL thickness is roughly independant on the the hot pressing time in both A and B composites.

The CL structure depends both on the matrix composition and on the hot pressing time. Let's compare the CL structure for the usual hot pressing time (10 mn). In the A composite, the structure is characteristic of highly misorientated turbostratic carbon (fig.4a). In the other composites, prepared with Nb₂O₅ containing matrices, the CL is much less organized. The structure generally exhibits very little turbostratic organization (fig. 4b). With increasing hot pressing times, the turbostratic character is more and more pronounced.

- The transition region (TR):

In all the composites, beyond the CL towards the fibre core, the HRTEM [5] had revealed a zone whose structure is neither that of the CL nor that of the fibre core (fig. 1).

The TR thickness depends on the matrix composition but not on the hot pressing time. It extends over about 40 nm in the A composite and about 100 nm in the other composites.

The TR structure and phase composition is independant on the matrix composition and on the hot pressing time. The density of SiC grains decreases towards zero from the fibre core to the CL. The TR phase composition was investigated by EELS in every composite. Next to the CL/TR interface the Si-L_{2,3} edge always exhibits the characteristics shown in figure 5. The phase composition is thus the same in all the composites. This EELS spectrum could correspond to a

convolution of SiO_2 and of a small amount of SiC . However, a previous study of B10 by AES and XPS demonstrates that SiOxCy is formed by fibre-matrix reaction [4]. The EELS analyses thus demonstrate that, in all the Nicalon/glass or glass ceramic composites studied, the TR contains SiOxCy . According to the EDX (fig. 6) and SIMS (fig. 7) concentration profiles, the amount of the SiOxCy is the highest next to the CL/TR interface and decreases towards the fibre core.

As a result, the fibre-matrix reaction results in an oxydation of the SiC contained in the fibre and the formation of carbon and silicon oxycarbide instead of SiO_2 as previously assumed. The reactivity of SiC seems related to the nanostructure of the different phases which form the Nicalon fibre. The microstructure of the SiOxCy rich phase is the same in all the composites. On the contrary the microstructure and the thickness of the carbon interphase depends on the matrix composition and on the hot pressing time.

Figure 1: HRTEM images of the fibre core (a) and of the transition region (b)
 SiC grains (arrows) are the only crystalline phase revealed by HRTEM and electronic diffraction.

- Interfaces:

The TR/fibre interface is progressive and does not form a real boundary. On the contrary, the CL/TR, the CL/glass or CL/NbC interfaces are always abrupt. Due to the shape of the NbC string, the NbC/CL and NbC/matrix interfaces are rather rough in the B, C, D and E composites. In the A composite, the (0002) basal planes of the turbostratic carbon tend to be parallel to the matrix/CL interface over a few interreticular spaces (fig 4a). Here and there, excrescences of the carbon layer penetrate deep into the matrix [5].

In the B, C, D and E composites, but not in the A composite, decohesion between the fibre and the matrix often derives from the foil preparation. It always occurs between the matrix and the NbC string (eg. fig 2b). The TEM studies do not reveal if the decohesion occurs at the NbC/CL interface or within one nanometer or so of the NbC/CL interface. Fissures are also observed in the E composite matrix. They are always stopped or deflected within the NbC string or at the NbC/CL interface (fig 3d).

Table 2: Microstructural and mechanical characteristics of the interphases and of the composites. The frictional stress is calculated using the Marshall's model [3]. σ_e is the elastic limit on the $\sigma=f(\epsilon)$ curves.

Material	fibre strength σ_{rf} (MPa)	composite		frictional stress (MPa)	carbon e (nm)	carbon structure
		σ_r (MPa)	σ_e (MPa)			
fibre	2460					
fibre+HF etch	2440					
fibre,20mn,1300°	1700					
A2	-	160	-	-	24	turbostratic (90%)
A10	890	460	-	54	30	"
A60	630	210	-	-	25	" (100%)
B2	-	650	250	-	130	little turbostratic organisation
B10	2230	800	200	10	130	"
B60	2500	1000	200	-	140	more pronounced organisation
B120	1300	420	200	-	130	"
C	1540	660	400	6.4	90	turbostratic (75%)
D	1700	700	400	-	90	little turbostratic organisation
E	1700	1150	300	-	80	"

Figure 2: TEM images of the interphases in the A2 (a) and B2 (b) composites. Arrows indicate the string of NbC grains.

INFLUENCE OF THE MIROSTRUCTURE ON THE MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR

The composite strength varies with the matrix composition and the hot pressing time. All the Nb₂O₅ containing matrix composites are tough whereas the A composite is brittle (table2).

The strength and toughness of long fibre reinforced composites depend on the relative value of the failure resistance of the interface and of the fibre.

Figures 3: TEM images of the interphases in the C (a), D (b), E (c,d) composites. The figure d shows a matrix fracture which is stopped or deviated by the NbC grains and consequently does not alter the fibre. Arrows indicate the NbC interphase.

Let's first discuss which parameters influence the fibre strength. The heat treatments result in a fibre strength degradation (table 2). The stresses sustained by the fibres during the composite fabrication may induce an evolution of the fibres defects and of the stresses applied to these defects. These influences could account for the variation of the fibre strength versus the matrix composition and hot pressing time experimentally observed.

Heat treatments change the microstructure and composition of the fibre periphery. The fibre strength seems to depend on the depth of these changes and particularly to be related with the thickness of the CL. No relationship between the CL microstructure and the fibre strength can be derived from the experimental results. The CL should act as a coating which is known to increase the fibre strength and thus counterbalance the negative effect of the heat treatments on the fibre strength.

The resistance to debonding and to sliding of the interface is the second parameter which governs composite strength and toughness. The question is now where is the mechanical fuse?

On the $\sigma=f(t)$ curves, the stress corresponding to the limit of the elastic behaviour, σ_e , which depends both on the matrix and on the resistance to failure at the interface, varies with the matrix composition (table 2). It does not depend on the hot pressing time in the B composites. Nanoindentations tests in A10, B10 and C composites [4,7] suggest that the decohesion occurs at one interface and not within a phase. This result supports Marshall [8] and Perez [9] work on similar composites but not Grande et al. [10].

The weakest link should be the CL/matrix interface for the following reasons:

- the progressive microstructural and compositional variations throughout the TR are not consistent with a decohesion between the TR and the fibre,
- decohesion is unlikely to occur at the CL/TR interface which is submitted to compressive stresses due to the thermal mismatch between the CL and the fibre,
- decohesion is likely to occur at the matrix/CL interface which is submitted to tensile stresses due to the thermal mismatch between the CL and the matrix. The thicker the CL is the higher the stresses are. The thermal mismatch between the fibre and the matrix in the C and D composites increases this phenomenon,
- TEM observations are consistent with a decohesion at the CL/matrix interface and more precisely at the interface CL/NbC. The thickness of the NbC layer likely plays a role on the decohesion. The thickest the layer is, the easiest the decohesion is. This easiest debonding would account for the better strength of the E composite compared to the C and D composites.

ROLE OF THE CARBON INTERFACE

From the study of these various Nicalon/glass or glass ceramic matrix composites the following conclusions can be derived.

- a carbon interphase does not necessarily promote toughness as demonstrated by the A composites. A previous study of Nicalon fibres/SiC-CVD composites resulted in the same conclusion [11],
- the parameter which determines the resistance to debonding and to sliding at the matrix-reinforcement interface is the adhesion of the carbon layer on the surrounding phases and not its microstructure. The influence of the carbon microstructure only plays a role through its possible influence on the adhesion. However, adhesion is not the only parameter which determines the decohesion location. As shown in a previous study of a SCS6/TA6V composite [12], the resistance to the sliding and thus the rugosity of the interface is also determinant. The carbon excrescences into the matrix observed in the A composites likely contribute to the high failure resistance of the interface,
- the toughness is not related to a layered structure of the carbon layer. In the studied tough composites, the carbon layer is poorly organized. Moreover, in the brittle composites (A), a layered structure is observed at the matrix/CL interface. Despite this layered structure the resistance to debonding and to sliding at the interface is higher in the A composites than in the other composites. This high failure resistance of the interface correlated to the low fibre strength results in the weakness and brittleness of the A composites. A layered structure was also observed at the carbon/fibre interface in brittle Nicalon fibres/SiC composites [11],
- the favorable influence of the Nb₂O₅ on the strength and toughness derives from its influence on the carbon layer width and on the adhesion between the carbon layer and the matrix.

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Figure 4: HRTEM images of typical microstructures of the carbon layer (CL).
 (a) The CL exhibits a highly measorientated turbostratic structure; a few (0002) planes are parallel to the CL/glass interface (b) The CL exhibits a poorly organized structure.

Figure 5: Si L2,3 edge characteristic of the fibre core (a) and of the transition region TR (b). The edge is characteristic of a convolution of SiC and SiOxCy in the fibre and of SiOxCy in the TR.

Figure 6

Figure 7

Figure 6: Concentration profile obtained by EDX in a thin cross section of the D composite. In the TR next to the CL/TR interface, it shows a peak in the oxygen concentration which is typical of all the composites. This peak corresponds to the maximum concentration of SiOxCy in the TR.

Figure 7: Concentration profile obtained by SIMS at the periphery of a fibre extracted from the B10 composite.

In the TR next to the CL/TR interface, it shows a peak in the O⁻/C⁻ and a depletion in the Si⁻/C⁻ values which are characteristic of all the composites and correspond to the maximum concentration of SiOxCy in the TR. The sputtering yield is about 15 nm/mn. The higher sensitivity of the SIMS explains why the compositional changes revealed by SIMS between t1 and t2 occur over much larger depth than the compositional changes detected by EDX. The diffusion of the matrix elements into the fibre is detected by SIMS over larger depth than the microstructural changes (CL+ TR).